

PSYCHOLOGICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR PROFESSIONAL PHARMACIST ACTIVITIES**Prof. Elmar Huseynov**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12704282>*

Abstract

Like every specialist, a pharmacist must have the psychological qualities necessary in their professional activity. The pharmaceutical industry, which covers the production of medicinal drugs to their sale to the population, requires from the individual specialist such psychological qualities that would allow them to professionally perform their work. The pharmaceutical organization of specialists has direct contact with the research and production laboratory with a variety of chemicals and contact with people in the pharmacy. An ideal specialist performs their professional activities effectively, without causing risk to themselves and others.

Keywords: *professional, activity, pharmacist, pharmacy, personality, psychology, formation, self-esteem, emotions, motivation, conscientiousness.*

The influence of the psyche of a specialist working in the pharmaceutical industry is especially relevant in modern society, where the pace of technology development leads to high demands on the professional's personality. They are subject to fundamentally new requirements, which affect not only the organization of production itself but also the entire trading process in pharmacy organizations. The ability to communicate with suppliers, and workers throughout the production process, as well as a special approach to patients in hospitals and pharmacies, because pharmacists play an essential role in the treatment of patients. Therefore, the psychological characteristics of a pharmacist influence the professional suitability of a specialist [2;4].

Professional suitability is the compliance of the individual psychological qualities of a specialist's personality, and their scientific knowledge with the modern requirements of the pharmacist profession. According to experts conducting research in this area, to be a good professional it is necessary to have the personal qualities that are necessary in the work of a pharmacist [3].

One of the main ones is communication skills, the ability to communicate, exchange information, and share knowledge. It will be difficult for a person who does not have these qualities to count on success in the professional activities of a pharmacist. The next quality necessary for the work of a pharmacist is empathy. If a person cannot closely perceive the problems of other people, he/she will not be able to understand them and provide the help that they need. Another important indicator of a pharmacist's personality structure is restraint. This quality is characterized by such strong-willed qualities as patience and self-control. Sociability, empathy, and restraint allow the pharmacist to develop their professional abilities, which allows them to increase the professional suitability of a specialist [4;6].

Along with these, a pharmacist needs good physical health; the profession of a pharmacist requires a certain amount of physical stress, endurance, and precision in the coordination of movements. The structure of the psychological qualities of a pharmacist's personality also includes such qualities as the ability to maintain self-control and composure in situations of psychological and emotional stress. The ability to listen and develop speech also needs to be developed by future specialists working in the pharmaceutical field.

Another direction in the modern pharmaceutical industry is pharmaceutical business managers, who are subject to certain psychological requirements. This is, first of all, logical thinking, then endurance, tact, attention, memory, intuition, etc. [2;3].

All these psychological qualities of a pharmacist's personality are necessary, also for the most difficult area of activity of this specialty – community pharmacy and hospital pharmacists working directly in contact with patients: the need to be sensitive to various aspects of the pharmacy assortment; sensitivity to speech for normal contact with the patient; high visual memory to quickly find the necessary medicine, as well as other medical products; focusing on the problems of a specific patient; stability of attention, to maintain performance throughout the working day; composure and restraint, especially important in situations of conflict; emotional stability and balance; diligence and conscientious fulfillment of their professional duties [5;7].

A pharmacist must be able to guide patients to the correct choice of medication, be polite and friendly, and try to take into account all aspects of effective treatment.

The most important thing in the work of a pharmacist is to choose an adequate psychological approach to the patient, which is a kind of psychotherapy. When communicating with hospital patients, the pharmacist

should provide general psychotherapy: information, explanation, reassurance, and emotional support; special psychotherapy: persuasion and suggestion; social therapy: empathy, shared joy in improving health, the joy of recovery, and active drug assistance [5;8].

To develop all of the above skills, a pharmacist must work on themselves, and cultivate a set of certain qualities necessary for successful professional activity in the field of pharmacy. It is necessary to work on the formation of personality, and constantly engage in self-actualization. Increase your scientific knowledge, and master the modern technology necessary for effective work.

Conclusions

1. Increasing the efficiency of a pharmacist's professional activity is a task that involves addressing various aspects such as personal, individual, and social characteristics of the pharmacist's personality, and developing flexible models for the specialist's role.

2. The activities of a pharmacist constitute a whole complex of personal and professional characteristics. The personality of a pharmacist is associated with qualities that depend on their professional activity.

3. The professional effectiveness of a pharmacist is associated with their individual psychological qualities.

4. The necessary professional qualities of a pharmacist are good nature, sociability, openness, the ability to resolve conflicts, and self-criticism.

5. The main aspect necessary in professional activity is the development of imagination and individual typological personality traits of a pharmacist.

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